

TESSe2b – THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDINGS. AN INTEGRATED SOLUTION FOR RESIDENTIAL BUILDING ENERGY STORAGE BY SOLAR AND GEOTHERMAL RESOURCES

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1. INTRODUCTION

Buildings are responsible for 40% of primary energy consumption and 36% of CO₂ emissions in the EU [1]. Nowadays, there is a compelling need for encouraging energy efficiency in buildings, enhance green technologies and promote advanced thermal energy storage solutions, to reduce radically energy consumption and minimize CO₂ emission. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) requires that all new buildings will be nearly zero-energy buildings by the end of 2020 [1]. To achieve this ambitious target is crucial to promote and develop renewable thermal technologies to provide ambient air space heating/cooling and domestic hot water (DHW). Different renewable thermal technologies can deliver heating and/or cooling at different temperature levels which define the suitability of different technologies for meeting specific heat requirements in the various sectors, from small domestic applications to large scale applications used in industrial processes and district heating and cooling networks. In the case of residential systems, the efficiency of the thermal infrastructure can be improved through the usage of small scale heat driven heating/cooling technologies like heat pumps and solar panels combined with thermal energy storage (TES). Thermal energy storage stocks thermal energy by heating or cooling a storage medium so that the energy can be used at a later time. TES can help balance energy demand and supply on a daily, weekly and even seasonal basis [2]. TESSe2b Project - Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings is an integrated solution for residential building energy storage by solar and geothermal resources. The main goal of the project is to design, develop, validate and demonstrate a modular and low cost thermal storage technology based on solar collectors and highly efficient geothermal heat pumps for heating, cooling and

DHW production for residential buildings. TESSe2b solution will be demonstrated at a single building in three pilot sites along Europe (Austria, Spain, and Cyprus) to assess its impact in different climates and provide evidences about TESSe2b overall technical and economic feasibility. TESSe2b is founded by H2020 program, project number 680555, Call identifier: H2020-EeB-2015 Call for EeB – Energy-efficient Buildings. The project as a total budget of 4.311.700 euros, 10 participants entities from eight countries (Portugal, Greece, Austria, Poland, Germany, Spain, U.K., Cyprus) IPS from Portugal is the project coordinator, the project had started in October 2015 and have a duration of 48 months.

2. TESSe2b SOLUTION

Tesse2b system combines commercial solar collectors and geothermal heat pump with innovative Latent thermal energy storage and enhanced geothermal boreholes HEs. The main components of the system are: the solar collectors, the inverter heat pump, geothermal boreholes, the hot modular thermal energy storage battery, the cold modular thermal energy storage battery, the DHW system and the in house heating/cooling devices. TESSe2b operation will be managed by a self-learning advanced controls system, in order, to optimize its overall performance. The general configuration of TESSe2b solution is shown in Figure 1. The solar thermal energy will produce DHW and supply the house heating demand. An inverter geothermal heat pump will provide space cooling for the building and DHW and space heating in the days where the solar thermal energy is not enough to supply the house heating demand. The latent thermal energy storage batteries are the main innovation of TESSe2b solution. Energy storage optimize the use of renewable energy, correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and the demand of energy in residential buildings. Another advantages of energy storage is uncoupled energy demand and production, what can be used to optimize the systems operating costs and balance the electric grid demands, shifting the HP operation for the lower electric tariff periods. Comparatively to common energy storage solutions (sensible heat storing) latent thermal energy storage presents two main advantages, the capacity of storing the energy at a constant and well defined temperature and a superior energy storage density.

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Figure 1. - TESSe2b Configuration

2.1 Latent Thermal Energy Storage Units

TESSe2b latent thermal storage batteries are modular plastic tanks with immersed finned coils heat exchangers, the unit capacity of the storage tank is around 150 l. The thermal energy storage batteries total

capacity is set by the number of modular units and the PCMs properties (volumetric latent heat). As is showed in Figure 1 the hot thermal latent storage tank HEs has two main circuits, one for charge the storage tank by the solar collectors and other for discharging the stored energy providing heat for the building. This circuit will also be used for charging the storage tanks by the geothermal heat pump. The HEs of the cold thermal latent energy storage tanks are similar but with a single main circuit that will be used to provide cooling for the house, during the PCM solidification. The same circuit is used to restore the PCM phase using the geothermal heat pump operating in cooling mode. A DHW based on PCMs is also developed to provide 200 l/day of hot water. The design of the DHW tank is similar to the hot storage tank, nevertheless, the discharge HEs circuits are longer, to increase the instantaneous heat transfer rate to the value required to produce DHW. Table 1 presents general characteristics of the thermal storage units developed in TESSe2b project.

Table 1. General characteristics of the TESSe2b latent thermal storage units

Unit	Storage temperature range °C	Net Unitary Volume (l)	Application
DHW unit	50-60	150	DHW production
Hot storage unit	42-48	150	Space heating
Cold Storage unit	7-12	150	Space cooling

Finite Elements Structural Analysis was used to optimize the structural design of the storage tanks and Computational fluids dynamics simulations (DFD) was developed to optimize the immersed HEs. The CFD approach was firstly validated based on experimental results obtained in a small scale prototype. After the validation process a CFD parametric study was developed to optimise the HEs design. The parameters studied were the tubes spacing, the fins pitch, the coils circuits length and mass flow rate of the heat transport fluid.

The design of the HEs to operate with hydrated slats PCMs included the development of an innovative thin film coating based on Aluminium Nitrate (AIN) to protect the HEs metal surfaces from the hydrated salts corrosion. The effectiveness of this solution was already proved by trial experiments in small Cu and Al specimens. Another innovation of the TESSe2b project is the development of nanoparticles enhanced paraffins to overcome the low thermal conductivity of organic PCMs and enhance the charge and discharge performance of the energy storage units. This work is ongoing, however, laboratorial tests have already proven that the dispersion of a small quantity of graphene based nanoparticle into the paraffins enhances significantly the thermal conductivity of the mixture and have a small effected in its latent heat, melting/solidification temperature and specific heat values.

2.2 Enhanced Borehole Heat Exchangers

Borehole Heat Exchangers (BHEs) are a well-established and reliable variety for the use of geothermal energy with heat pumps. One of TESSe2b project goals is to develop a BHE that can also be used for the storage of thermal energy thus supporting the system in order to increase its performance in the heating and cooling mode. During the operation of the heat pump in heating mode the temperature of the heat carrier fluid within the BHE will decrease, during cooling it will increase (Figure 2). As the heat transfer in the ground is mainly conductive and its thermal diffusivity is low this leads to a much slower ground thermal response than the heat pump requirements, resulting in thermal waves being transmitted into the ground through the BHEs. This causes a lower coefficient of performance (COP) of the ground source heat pump (GSHP). To improve the effectiveness of the BHEs, adding PCMs to the grout material is regarded an effective means to store thermal energy in the BHEs. Thus, the generated thermal wave should be smoothened, thus increasing the SPF (seasonal performance factor) of the heat pump system. The expected impact on a heating application is illustrated in Figure 2.

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Figure 2. Calculated temperatures of the heat carrier fluid within a BHE during one year, heating and cooling and expected impact of the implemented PCMs (green line) [3].

As mentioned before in the case of heating the temperature of the heat carrier fluid within the BHEs will decrease during the operating time of the heat pump. In view of the expected low temperature the selected PCM should provide energy in a temperature range between the low values and the temperatures of the surrounding soil, so the PCM can support the system by stabilizing the temperatures at a higher level during the operation of the heat pump. During the shut-down period, the PCMs will be recharged by the natural soil heat flow. In cooling mode, the PCM will help to stabilize the temperature at a lower level storing the heat provide by the heat transport fluid, the PCM will discharge this energy to the soil during the shut-down period. The selection of the appropriate PCMs to be integrated into the borehole is closely connected with the PCM phase transition temperature the soil undisturbed temperature and the main operation mode of the heat pump (heating/cooling).

2.3 Self-learning Advanced Control System

TESSe2b control system ensures the correct and efficient operation of the entire solution. This is done by an intelligent (adaptive) system that monitors in each moment the inlet and outlet temperature of the heating and cooling devices of the building and adapts the flow and the temperature of the heat transfer fluid in order to ensure that the house will be properly heated, cooled or dehumidified. One of the objectives of the intelligent control system is short-term forecast of the important parameters of the system and the time at which they will be achieved. The controller will also ensure that there is always DHW for the users. The TESSe2b controller will additionally regulate the temperature inside the PCM storage tanks, in order to operate within the PCMs safety limits and to perform accordingly to other safety requirements, such as the Legionella prevention and the operation in extreme weather conditions. The TESSe2b controller can operate with a range of different heating and cooling devices, such as: underfloor or in-wall pipes, radiators, fan coils etc. The controller ensures that the inlet temperature of the house will be the necessary to heat or cool the building. Each room should be controlled by a decentralized control device and thermostat, which is not be part of the TESSe2b system. TESSe2b solution can be installed not only in new building but also in buildings with pre-existing heating and cooling system, without replacing the heating and cooling circuit units, thus making the system more affordable. Additionally, the TESSe2b system will also have an integrated monitoring system to collect and store measurement data for the real-time and off-line performance evaluation of the system.

The main functions that TESSe2b assures to the installed building are: Domestic Hot Water production (DHW operating mode), Ambient Cooling (Cooling operation mode) and Ambient Heating (Heating operation mode). Three other operating modes are included, the Idle State: No heat transfers (IDLE state mode), Holiday Mode and Service Mode. Table 2 shows all the TESSe2b operating modes.

Table 2. TESSe2b operating modes [4]

Description	Mode	From	To
DHW boiler charging by Solar Collectors	DHW	Solar Collectors	Domestic Hot Water Boiler
DHW boiler charging by Heat Pump	DHW	Heat Pump	Domestic Hot Water Boiler
DHW boiler charging by Backup Heater	DHW	Backup Heater	Domestic Hot Water Boiler
DHW boiler charging by BUH for Legionella Protection	DHW	Backup Heater	Domestic Hot Water Boiler
Hot PCM charging by Solar Collectors	Heating	Solar Collectors	Hot PCM Storage
Hot PCM charging by Heat Pump	Heating	Heat Pump	Hot PCM Storage
Building heating by HPCM	Heating	Hot PCM Storage	Building Terminal Units
Building heating by HPCM and Heat Pump	Heating	Hot PCM Storage & HP	Building Terminal Units
Building heating by Heat Pump	Heating	Heat Pump	Building Terminal Units
Overheating prevention	Heating	Solar Collectors	Heat Dissipater
Cold PCM charging by Heat Pump	Cooling	Heat Pump	Cold PCM Storage
Building cooling by CPCM	Cooling	Cold PCM Storage	Building Terminal Units
Building cooling by CPCM and Heat Pump	Cooling	Cold PCM Storage & HP	Building Terminal Units
Building cooling by Heat Pump	Cooling	Heat Pump	Building Terminal Units
Building cooling by Heat Pump & Dehumidification	Cooling	Heat Pump	Building Terminal Units
Idle State: No heat transfers	-	-	-
Holiday Mode (to be defined if needed)	-	-	-
Service Mode (to be defined if needed)	-	-	-

3. DEMONSTRATION SITES

Demonstration and on-site monitoring evaluation of small scale TESSe2b solution at a single building in three pilot sites along Europe, Austria, Spain and Cyprus (Figure 3) will be conducted with the aim of evaluating the system's integration into building space, the impact of TESSe2b solution in different climates and to provide evidence about its overall technical and economic feasibility.

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Spain

Austria

Cyprus

Figure 3. Photos of the three demo sites (Austria, Spain and Cyprus)

To characterize the heating and cooling energy needs of the three demo sites dynamic energy simulations of the buildings have been made. The simulations were developed by Design Builder software [5] which is validated by ANSI/ASHRAE standard 140. To have a precise idea of the houses thermal performance were developed simulations for the real houses and for houses with the same architecture design, but considering the thermal envelope reference, defined by the regulation of the respective countries.

3.1 Spanish demo site

The demosite house of Spain is located in Calonge de Segarra in Catalonia region, is an old house with 130 m² equally distributed by two floors, the building is made of limestone and the external walls have a thin layer of polyurethane as thermal isolation. The energy building simulation predicted a heating capacity of 11.3 kW and the cooling capacity is 5.04 kW. The annual specific energy needs is 46.38 kWh/(m².y) for heating and 8.93 kWh/(m².y) for cooling. Comparing with the results obtained by the reference thermal envelope the real building has similar energy needs, slightly higher than the reference.

3.2 Austrian demo site

The selected house is placed in Gratz is a single floor house with an occupied area of 185 m². The building is of brick plastered walls and has an 18 cm thickness layer of expanded polyurethane. Results from the energy building simulation for from three days of March and July are shown in Figure 4. The simulation predicted heating capacity is 14.39 kW and the cooling capacity is 4.67 kW. The annual specific energy needs is 55.08 kWh/(m².y) for heating and 8.67 kWh/(m².y) for cooling. Comparing with the reference thermal envelope building it the real building has similar energy needs, slightly higher than the reference (more 12%) for heating and slightly lower for cooling (less 14%).

3.3 Cyprus demo site

The selected property is a residential house in Meliou village, a small traditional village, 35 km from Pafos town airport and 14 km from the Latchi beach area. The surface of the house is 180 m² (100 m² of ground floor and 80 m² of first floor). It is built in a plot of 3500m², which is at a high of 420 m from the sea level. The building is of brick plastered walls and roof tiling. The underground area is rich in geothermal energy due to the number of water springs and underground waters. The house is 28 years old and it's in good condition. The energy building simulation for the Cyprus demo site predicted a heating capacity of 17.03 kW and the cooling capacity of 18.56 kW. The annual specific energy needs is 45.34 kWh/(m².a) for heating and 69.92 kWh/(m².a) for cooling. Comparing with the simulation developed with the reference values for the thermal envelope of the building the real house has higher needs of heating (more 106%) and cooling (more 40%).

3.4 TESSe2b solution for Spain demosite

The main characteristic of TESSe2b solution for Spain demosites are presented in Table 3. The number of hot thermal storage units was selected to maximize the house heating needs covered by solar thermal energy. The number of cold thermal storage units were selected, based on a different criteria, the cold thermal storage battery capacity was dimensioned to minimize the geothermal heat pump operation during the higher electric tariff hours.

Table 3. Main characteristic of TESSe2b solution for Spain demosite

Solar Collectors Type	Number of Collectors	Total Area (m ²)
Selective Flat plate	9	22.6
Geothermal Heat Pump Type	Heating Capacity	Cooling Capacity

Inverter	12 kW	9.5 kW
Number of HPCM tanks	Nominal Storage Temperature	PCM
4	44 °C	Paraffin A44
Number of CPCM tanks	Nominal Storage Temperature	PCM
2	9 °C	Paraffin A9
Number PCM DHW tank	Nominal Storage Temperature	PCM
1	53 °C	Paraffin A53
BHEs	Number of boreholes	PCM
U tubes; 40 mm diameter;	4 x 90 m; total 360 m	To de defined based on TRT results

Figure 4 presents the predicted heating and cooling needs for Spain demosite house, along three consecutive days over the heating and the cooling season. Figure 4. also shows the solar collectors incident radiation and the house heating and cooling needs provided directly by the geothermal heat pump and the thermal energy storage batteries. The results presented in Figure 4 clearly show how the thermal storage batteries can optimize the use of solar energy and provides flexibility to the system to shift the heat pump operation for the lower electric tariff periods, particularly, during the cooling season.

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Figure 4. Energy day profiles for Spain house demosite

4. EXPECTED BENEFITS

The target of TESSe2b H2020 Project - Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings is to develop an integrated solution for residential building application that combines solar and geothermal energy sources with latent thermal energy storage. The main expected benefits of TESSe2b solution comparatively with common heating, cooling and DHW productions systems for residential buildings are:

- To increase the use of renewable energy sources and consequently reduce the CO₂ emissions of residential buildings.
- To reduce the overall operational cost and balance of the electric grid energy demand. Thermal energy storing not only enables the enhance use of renewable energy sources, but also provides operational flexibility to the system, detaching the building thermal energy demand from its production, shifting the thermal energy production devices operation to the lower electric tariff hours.

Comparatively to common thermal energy storage systems for residential building, based on sensible heat, TESSe2b solution also presents advantages, such as:

- A superior energy storage density, which can increase significantly the thermal energy storage capacity in small volumes, this issue is particularly relevant for residential buildings that in general have limited free space available.
- Store the energy at a constant well-defined temperature, a practical benefit of this is to reduce the maximum temperature level of thermal energy storage for heating and increase the minimum temperature level of thermal energy storage for cooling. Increasing the overall systems efficiency and reduce thermal isolation costs.

5. CONCLUSIONS

TESSe2b H2020 Project - Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings was been presented. TESSe2b main objective is to develop an integrated solution for residential building energy storage by solar and geothermal resources that will enable the optimal use of renewable energy and provide advantageous solutions for correcting the mismatch that often occurs between the supply and demand of energy in residential buildings. As general benefits of TESSe2b solution we can point:

- One single appliance provides heating and cooling of ambient residential air;
- The maintenance costs and time are reduced compared to the conventional separate equipment, based on fossil fuel sources (boilers and HVAC equipment);
- Reduction in implementation space (only one equipment for both HVAC and DHW);
- Reduction of noise (no exterior condensing units necessary);
- Possible higher equipment performance due to favourable ground temperatures and solar utilization;
- Reduction of CO₂ fingertip when compared to traditional boilers and AVAC equipment, due to the utilization of renewable energy sources (solar and geothermal) and the utilization of thermal accumulation;
- Reduction on the monthly operation cost due to the possible operation of unit during reduced tariff rates of energy and energy accumulation.

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